

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY OF TEACHERS IN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

This method is employed in the research of this article to the classification of types of professional and pedagogical tasks related to the preparation of an educator for professional activities for the implementation of education on the basis of digital technologies.

РАЗВИТИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ПЕДАГОГИ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯХ НА ОСНОВЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

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ABSTRACT

Данный метод использован в исследовании данной статьи для классификации видов профессионально-педагогических задач, связанных с подготовкой педагога к профессиональной деятельности по реализации образования на основе цифровых технологий.

Introduction. In modern conditions, the development of Science and technology requires a radical change in the requirements for education and its results, and the creation of standards of a new generation based on this basis makes the era itself an important task for educators. The educational standards created today are required to be based on digital technologies. That is why modern pedagogy and today's pedagogical research are turning the development of educational technologies on the basis of digital technologies into an urgent task.

The upbringing of teachers as an independent, responsible, socially mobilizing person is required to develop social skills in them in order to successfully socialize them and prepare them for finding a worthy place in the labor market. To implement such an approach, it is important pedagogical importance to comprehensively support future educators in the educational and cognitive process. The process of pedagogical support is mainly aimed at students.

In our opinion, one of the structural elements of the pedagogical process based on digital technologies is educational tools, which serve to visually present educational materials in the educational process, to learn, as well as to improve the effectiveness of education - educational tools. As a result of the appropriate use of educational tools, the rapid study of students' educational materials, long storage in memory, comprehension, the emergence of motivation in the study of subjects of science, leads to an increase in interest.

Theoretical part. To improve the digital technologies used in the educational process, educators are advised: "technical means of Education: internet, network-connected computers, interactive whiteboard, multimedia tools, computer classes with basic and additional devices, to establish the use of electronic study halls with Wi-Fi connection; " auxiliary means of Education: various models, discs with electronic educational resources, video films used in teaching, flash memory, visual; didactic tools of Education: Educational and methodological manuals with the possibility of management, educational, supervisory e-learning resources, electronic educational and methodological complexes, methodological guidelines and the use of e-learning modules during training; it is necessary to quickly master the new educational tools that are entering the educational process and apply and formulate in the organization of pedagogical activity". Such digital technologies are a requirement of today's modern education and an opportunity to master it qualitatively, quickly and easily. Hence, digital technologies are an important factor in the effectiveness and productivity of the pedagogical process.

The development of professional competence in the pedagogical process is influenced by the personal rise of educators and manifests the following qualities in them:

Cognitive adjectives are skills to be able to feel the surrounding world, to ask questions, to seek out the cause of events, to express whether or not they understand the essence of the question.

1. Creative qualities include inspiration, fantasy, sharpness of mind, elegance to confrontation, clarity of thought and emotion, self-reflection.
2. Methodological (organizational activity) qualities include the ability to determine the purpose of educational activities and be able to explain them, the ability to set goals for oneself, the ability to reflexive thinking.

Also, organizational functioning (methodological) qualities are manifested in cognition and creativity in the process of organizing the education of students:

- knowledge of the characteristics of the student's own individual activity;
 - being able to understand and explain its purpose through training with educational subjects;
 - appropriate goal, availability of content-appropriate programs, completion of the work started, commitment to the goal, commitment to the goal and commitment to achieve the goal;
 - being able to put the educational goal in a given area before oneself, to create a plan for success, to fulfill the established plan based on one's individual abilities, to achieve and realize one's own result, to compare one's own results with those of classmates;
 - the formation of the rules of activity, the formation of a system of its laws;
- self-organization skills: activity planning, programming, activity ethics and methods correction (editing), activity ordering, alternative in the mind at the same time holding thoughts:
- self-control, analysis and evaluation;
 - to be able to enter into a relationship with other subjects of education and the surrounding world, to be able to stand up in one's own idea, to defend, to be assertive;
 - the ability to organize creativity in others, learn and process the ideas of other students, be able to organize a mental attack, participate in it, compare ideas, conduct debates and discussions. To develop such abilities, it is used in the educational process in the formation of their heuristic qualities, educational goals. In this sense, a new educational activity should be directed by the student to create a creative educational product.

The system of training educators for professional pedagogical activity through digital technologies should be based on the principles of ownership of a scientific nature, continuity, systematicity and unity of theoretical and practical training.

It is known that today the labor market objectively requires a socially and professionally competent, dialectical-minded, deeply knowledgeable, culture-aware and competitive personality.

Each assignment included the following types: training-logical research, research, creative evaluation, and Correction. The universal types of these tasks will have their own characteristics, which are determined by the tasks of each type of training within the framework of each task.

References:

1. Умаров Ш. Выражение вторичных многочленов спектральными коэффициентами //Engineering problems and innovations. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 20-26.
2. Umarov S. A. Research on General Mathematical Characteristics of Boolean Functions' Models and Their Logical Operations and Table Replacement in Cryptographic Transformations //Journal of Optoelectronics Laser. – 2022. – Т. 41. – №. 10. – С. 126-133.
3. Umarov, Bekzod. "RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VOSITASIDA PEDAGOGLARNING PROFESSIONAL KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MAZMUNI." Евразийский журнал математической теории и компьютерных наук 3.5 (2023): 87-93.
4. Umarov B. [PRINCIPLES OF FORMING TEACHER COMPETENCE THROUGH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES](#)
5. Умаров Б. А. КОРХОНА ВА ТАШКИЛОТЛАР БОШҚАРУВИНИНГ МОДЕЛЛАШТИРИШДА АВТОМАТЛАШТИРИЛГАН АХБОРОТ ТИЗИМЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ

//Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 2. – С. 117-122.

6. Azizovich U. B. RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA PEDAGOGLARNING PROFESSIONAL KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI //FarDU. ILMIY XABARLAR-1 (115-117). – 2023.

7. Azizovich U. B. Ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalar va uning pedagoglar kasbiy faoliyatidagi imkoniyatlari //FarDU. ILMIY XABARLAR–НАУЧНЫЙ ВЕСТНИК. ФЕРГУ. – 2022.

8. Азизович У. Б., Азизжонович У. Ш. Жадвалли алмаштиришлар асосидаги симметрик блокчи шифрлаш алгоритмининг криптобардошлик критерийлари //Ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари ва телекоммуникацияларнинг замонавий. – 2021.

9. Азизович У. Б., Азизжонович У. Ш. Ахборотни хавфсизлиги масалаларида хэш-функциянинг қўлланилиши //Ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари ва телекоммуникацияларнинг замонавий. – 2020.

10. Азизович У. Б. Ўқитишда кейс-методдан фойдаланиш масалалари //INFORMATIKA, AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA BOSHQARUV TIZIMI: BUGUN VA KELAJAKDA. – 2018.

11. Азизович У. Б. Ўқув жараёнига инновацион таълим технологияларини жорий этиш заруряти //INFORMATIKA, AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA BOSHQARUV TIZIMI: BUGUN VA KELAJAKDA. – 2018.

12. Азизович У. Б. Мультимедиа ишланмаларининг бугунги кун ҳолати ва истекболлари //INFORMATIKA, AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA BOSHQARUV TIZIMI: BUGUN VA KELAJAKDA. – 2018.

13. Азизжонович У. Ш. Сигналларни спектрал усул ёрдамида иккинчи даражали кўпхад кўринишида ифодалаш //Тенденции и перспективы развития науки и образования в условиях глобализации. – 2015.

14. Азизович У. Б. Мультимедиага ўқув методик мажмуа архитектураси //Ахборот ва телекоммуникация технологиялари муоммолари илмий-техник. – 2015.

15. Ibragimovna, U.B. A.U.M. (2020). THE PROBLEM OF APPROXIMATING SIGNALS BASED ON MODELING OF WAVELET-HAAR TRANSFORMATION. EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 6(11), 502-506.

16. Умаров Бекзод Азизович. Масофавий таълим тизимларини ташкил этишда LMS тизимларидан фойдаланиш масалалари.

17. B.Umarov. [RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VOSITASIDA PEDAGOGLARNING PROFESSIONAL KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MAZMUNI-2023](#)